

FLUTTER SUPPRESSION OF COMPOSITE PLATES USING OPTICAL FIBER SENSORS AND PIEZOELECTRIC ACTUATORS

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SUMMARY: For lightweight and flexible structures, it is important to measure and suppress the vibrations induced by interactions between fluid and structures. In recent years, several applications of active control to aeroelastic system have been studied in order to favorably modify the behavior of aeroelastic systems. This paper investigates dynamic application of a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor system and the adaptive vibration control of a composite plate with a surface-bonded FBG sensor and piezoelectric actuators. For the detection of Bragg wavelength changes, Fabry-Perot read-out interferometers are used. The FBG sensor signal is used for evaluating stability boundary of an aeroelastic system and feedback control. Neuro-adaptive feedback control algorithm is applied to the flutter suppression of the composite plate. The real-time implementation of the adaptive controller is performed using a digital signal processor (DSP). The effectiveness of the control system is validated via wind tunnel testing. The experimental results are provided in the time and frequency domain. It is shown that the amplitude of flutter mode and its harmonics are reduced when the control law is applied.

KEYWORDS: smart structure, fiber Bragg grating, piezoelectric actuator, flutter suppression, neural-network controller

INTRODUCTION

For lightweight and flexible structures, it is important to measure and suppress the flow-induced vibrations caused by interactions between fluid and structures. Dynamic aeroelastic instability, flutter, involves aerodynamic, inertia and elastic forces of flight structures. Because flutter may cause disastrous structural failure in flight, the prediction of stability boundary and the suppression of flutter are very important in flight structures.

Conventionally, the damping ratio of the critical mode has been used to evaluate the stability of an aeroelastic system. However, the estimation of modal damping is so sensitive to noise and error that it is difficult to obtain accurate and reliable data from test. Furthermore, for an explosive type of flutter, the damping parameter shows no sign of instability up to the neighborhood of the critical speed. Therefore, a more suitable parameter is required for a better flutter prediction. Torri and Matsuzaki [1] proposed a flutter prediction parameter effectively applicable to the numerical model obtained by experimental system identification. We adopted their method for the evaluation of stability boundary.

In recent years, several active control strategies have been studied in order to favorably modify the behavior of aeroelastic systems [2]. One of the main objectives of the aeroelastic control is flutter suppression. Typically, control surfaces such as spoilers and flaps have been used to generate auxiliary aerodynamic lift and moment. The active flexible wing program has demonstrated the flutter suppression of a fighter-type scaled model in various maneuver modes by utilizing control surfaces and active control technology at NASA Langley research center [3]. The Benchmark Active Control Technology (BACT) model has been used as an active control test bed for evaluating new and

innovative control methodologies [4].

Recent development of smart materials and structures gives us another alternative for active flutter suppression. Lazarus *et al.* [5] successfully applied multi-input multi-output controls to suppress vibration and flutter of a plate-like lifting surface with surface-bonded piezoelectric actuators. Han *et al.* [6] performed numerical and experimental investigation on active flutter suppression of a swept-back cantilevered plate. The aeroelastic model was determined in the state space equation using a finite element method, a panel aerodynamic method, and a rational function approximation. Robust controllers were designed and validated through wind tunnel experiment. Application of piezoelectric actuation to flutter control of a more realistic wing model was achieved under the piezoceramic aeroelastic response tailoring investigation (PARTI) program at NASA Langley research center [7].

This paper investigates dynamic application of a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor system and the adaptive vibration control of a composite plate with a surface-bonded FBG sensor and piezoelectric actuators. The principle of the FBG sensor is based on the measurement of the changes in reflective signal, which is the center wavelength of back-reflected light from a Bragg grating, and depends on the effective refractive index of the core and the periodicity of the grating. A simple optically passive detection scheme is used in the present study. This detection scheme is based on two cavity lengths in Fabry-Perot read-out interferometers to produce two quadrature phase shifted signals from Bragg grating sensor. The acquired FBG sensor signal is used for evaluating stability boundary of an aeroelastic system and feedback control. Neuro-adaptive feedback control algorithm is applied to the flutter suppression of a composite plate. Among several control methodologies, the indirect model reference adaptive controller is used. The control system consists of the neuro-identification model and the neuro-controller. The real-time implementation of the adaptive controller is performed using a digital signal processor (DSP). The effectiveness of the flutter suppression system is evaluated via wind tunnel testing.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The test model is a swept-back cantilevered plate with a surface bonded FBG sensor and piezoceramic actuators. The base plate is $[90_2/0_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate (CU-125 NS, HANKUK FIBER). Two piezoceramics (C-82, Fuji Ceramics) are bonded on the surface close to leading edge and one FBG sensor ($\lambda_B = 1546$ nm) is bonded on the surface close to trailing edge as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the test model.

Wind tunnel test has been performed in the subsonic wind tunnel at the Department of Aerospace Engineering, KAIST. The wind tunnel is an open-circuit tunnel with effective velocity ranges of 9 to 60 m/sec and closed test section. In order to measure the vibration of the test model, an FBG sensor, a PVDF sensor and laser displacement sensors (LB301, KEYENCE) are used. The locations of each sensor are described in Fig. 1. Control law is applied at the free stream velocities that cause limit cycle oscillations. The FBG sensor signal is fed into the controller, which is implemented on a DSP board (DS1102, dSPACE). The sampling frequency used is 1 kHz, which is high enough compared with the dominant frequency of the system. The generated control input is applied to the piezoceramics through a high voltage amplifier (SQV3/500). The experimental setup for flutter suppression is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Experimental setup for flutter suppression.

FBG SENSOR SYSTEM

Recently, FBG sensors have been increasingly studied as optical sensors for a variety of applications; health monitoring, vibration measurement, nondestructive testing and so on. These applications are based on the same principle; the measurement of Bragg wavelength shift. Therefore, it needs to measure the Bragg wavelength shift as fast as possible to detect high frequency phenomena [8]. Kersey *et al.* [9] proposed a method to detect the wavelength shift of an FBG utilizing an unbalanced fiber interferometer. Lo [10] designed a simple optically passive detection scheme for FBG using two Fabry-Perot read-outs to produce two quadrature phase shifted signals. These schemes could be used

to measure high-frequency micro-vibration, such as acoustic emission and small mechanical vibration. In this paper, the FBG sensor system, which adopted the scheme designed by Lo [10], fabricated by Kim *et al.* [8] was used to measure flow-induced vibration.

Fig. 3 shows the schematic of the sensor system. The system consists of a broadband source, four 2x2 couplers, two extrinsic Fabry-Perot cavities, two photo-detectors and FBG sensor. The light emitted from the broadband source passes through the coupler #1. The light reflected back by the FBG is divided into two lights by the coupler #2. A pair of lights is guided to two read-out interferometers by the coupler #3 and #4, respectively. The two read-out interferometers are two low finesse Fabry-Perot cavities in air. The pair of lights reflected by the Fabry-Perot cavities is measured by two photo-detectors. Since the two read-out interferometers have different cavity lengths, the reflecting Bragg wavelength falls on different spectral locations of the two Fabry-Perot spectral transfer functions as shown in Fig. 4. It is important that the two quadrature-shifted signals can be adjusted by keeping the two Fabry-Perot spectrums in quadrature. When measuring small phase shifts, it is desirable to operate along the linear region of the response curve i.e. the region between the peaks and valleys. Therefore, it is possible to detect the signal within the linear region because the two intensities are measured simultaneously and at least one of them is in quadrature [8].

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of FBG sensor system.

Figure 4. Power spectra of two Fabry-Perot interferometers and FBG [8].

AEROELASTIC STABILITY EVALUATION

A flutter prediction parameter proposed by Torri and Matsuzaki [1] was used for the evaluation of stability boundary of the test model. The method consists of two parts: system identification with an ARMA model and evaluation of flutter prediction parameter.

An aeroelastic system is continuously excited by the turbulence of airstreams that can be considered as white noise. The sampled data $y(k)$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, N$) are considered to be a random vibration, which can be described by an AR or ARMA model. The ARMA model describing a random vibration is as follows:

$$\alpha(z^{-1})y(k) = \beta(z^{-1})e(k) \quad (1)$$

where, $e(k)$ is white noise, $\alpha(z^{-1})$ and $\beta(z^{-1})$ are AR and MA parts, respectively. Torri and Matsuzaki [1] considered only two-mode coupled flutter case. Therefore, the system dynamics are expressed by the fourth-order equation. The characteristic polynomial is expressed by the AR part.

$$G(z) = A_4 z^4 + A_3 z^3 + A_2 z^2 + A_1 z + A_0 = A_4 (z - z_1)(z - z_2)(z - z_3)(z - z_4) \quad (2)$$

where $z_3 = z_1^*$ and $z_4 = z_2^*$.

The stability condition of the system is that all roots are located within a unit circle in the Gauss plane. The system is neutrally stable if any root is located in the circumference of the unit circle, which is considered the flutter boundary. Jury's determinant method is a way of finding stability boundary using a characteristic polynomial. The necessary and sufficient conditions that the system is stable are that all of the followings are positive:

$$\begin{aligned} G(1) &= A_4 + A_3 + A_2 + A_1 + A_0 \\ G(-1) &= A_4 - A_3 + A_2 - A_1 + A_0 \\ F^+(k) &= \det(\mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{Y}_k) \quad (k=1,3) \\ F^-(k) &= \det(\mathbf{X}_k - \mathbf{Y}_k) \quad (k=1,3) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{X}_k = \begin{bmatrix} A_4 & \cdots & A_{4-k+1} \\ 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & A_4 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{Y}_k = \begin{bmatrix} A_{k-1} & \cdots & A_0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & 0 \\ A_0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The parameter $F^-(3)$ is expressed as follows:

$$F^-(3) = A_4^3 \prod_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i < j}}^4 (1 - z_i z_j) = A_4^3 |1 - z_1 z_2|^2 |1 - z_1 z_2^*|^2 (1 - |z_1|^2)(1 - |z_2|^2) \quad (4)$$

$F^-(3)$ becomes zero at the flutter boundary, where either $|z_1|=1$ or $|z_2|=1$ is satisfied. Therefore, $F^-(3)$ can be used as the flutter predictor. Because its behavior against dynamic pressure ($q = 1/2(\rho_{air} U_\infty^2)$, ρ_{air} is air density and U_∞ is airflow velocity) is quadratic, they proposed new flutter prediction parameter that is almost linear against dynamic pressure.

$$F_z = \frac{F^-(3)}{F^-(1)^2} = \frac{\det(\mathbf{X}_3 - \mathbf{Y}_3)}{(A_4 - A_0)^2} \quad (5)$$

This is applicable for two-mode flutter system. Torri and Matsuzaki [1] validated this parameter through the supersonic wind-tunnel testing. In the present study, eq. (5) is used for the evaluation of flutter boundary. The MATLAB is used for estimation of AR coefficients and the flutter boundary is calculated by a linear fitting of F_z .

NEURAL-NETWORK CONTROLLER

Neural network is a mathematical model, which is artificially embodied by imitating recognition or knowledge-acquiring process of human beings. A neural network consists of neurons, weights and biases. Learning is defined as a process that tunes weights and biases to obtain the desired output values of the neural network.

Overall structure and learning algorithm of the neural network are similar to those of reference [11].

The neural network used in this study consists of one input vector and two layers; one hidden layer and one output layer. Tangent sigmoid activation function was used for the hidden layer, and linear activation function was used for the output layer. For the simplification, any bias was not used in the network.

Among several learning algorithms, error back-propagation learning rule is used, and the momentum method is applied in order to improve convergence characteristics and the convergent speed. The fundamental idea of the algorithm is to adjust weights and biases of neural network so that the sum of squared error of outputs is to be minimized. Using gradient descent procedure, weights are updated in real-time.

The control system consists of the neuro-identification model and the neuro-controller, and the overall architecture of the controller is shown in Fig. 5. The role of the neural network model (identifier) for the plant is to obtain mathematical representation of the real plant. This procedure is called forward modeling. The neural network model is located in parallel with the plant. The weights of the neural network model are adjusted so that the output of the neural network model should be the same as that of the plant. The input vector of the neural network model consists of the present and previous plant inputs and outputs. In other words, the output value of neural network model, y_m is calculated by using time sequences of the plant input, u and plant output, y_p as follows:

$$y_m(t+1) = f(y_p(t), \dots, y_p(t-n); u(t), \dots, u(t-m)) \quad (6)$$

Figure 5. Overall architecture for neuro-controller with neural-network model.

After completing the forward modeling, the tuning for weights of the neuro-controller is performed by the error back-propagation learning algorithm. Because the desired output value of the neuro-controller is not given in advance, this value should be calculated by the error back-propagation through the neural network plant model, as shown in Fig. 6. In this step, the desired output value of the plant is set to zero because the purpose of the control is to suppress vibrations. When adjusting the weights of the neuro-controller, those of the neural network model are not changed. The output of the neuro-controller, u_c is calculated by using time sequences of the plant output, y_p as follows:

$$u_c(t) = f(y_p(t-1), y_p(t-2), \dots, y_p(t-n)) \quad (7)$$

Figure 6. Connection of neural-network model and neuro-controller.

The neuro-controller has 5 input values, 8 neurons and 1 neuron for the hidden and output layers, respectively. The output value of the neuro-controller is used as both the control force of the plant and the 5-th input of neural network model. Here, the control force is the applied voltage to the piezoceramic actuator. The 5 previous output values of plant are used as input of neuro-controller. The neural network model has the same structure as neuro-controller. Four previous output values of plant and output of neuro-controller are used as the input values of the neural network model.

ANALYTIC AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

At first, modal testing was performed and compared with the result of the MSC/NASTRAN. The material properties of CU-125 NS is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 = 119\text{GPa}, E_2 = 8.67\text{GPa}, G_{12} = G_{13} = 5.18\text{GPa}, \\
 G_{23} = 3.29\text{GPa}, \nu_{12} = 0.31, \rho = 1570\text{kg/m}^3, t = 0.11\text{mm}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

Modal frequencies are shown in Table 1. In the analysis process, structural effects of piezoceramics and optical fiber was not considered. The experimental modal frequencies are less than analytic solution as a whole. It may be caused by inaccurate material properties. The MSC/NASTRAN was also used for the aeroelastic analysis. V-g plot is shown in Fig. 7 and the flutter speed calculated is $V_F = 15.43$ m/s. Positive damping in V-g analysis denotes the aeroelastic instability. Refer to reference [12] for the V-g method for the flutter analysis.

Table 1. Modal frequencies of the test model.

Mode No.	Modal frequency [Hz]	
	Experiment	MSC/NASTRAN
1	6.89	7.56
2	17.44	18.35
3	47.81	48.56
4	56.91	58.46

Figure 7. V-g plot of the composite plate model. **Figure 8.** Power spectra vs. airflow velocity.

When the airflow velocity is below 14.0 m/s, air damping is dominant and the aeroelastic system is stable. As the airflow velocity increases, the limit cycle oscillation occurs and the vibration amplitude increases according to the increase of airflow velocity. Power spectra of the FBG sensor data against airflow velocity are shown in Fig. 8. It can be seen that the vibration energy is concentrated in the second mode, which is flutter mode as shown in Fig. 7, and increases according to airflow velocity.

In case of interpreting analytical result, the flutter phenomenon breaks out suddenly and the stability boundary is clear. However, in practical situation, there is a limit cycle oscillation region and it is difficult to determine the flutter point. In addition, limit cycle oscillation could lead to fatigue failure. The stability boundary has been evaluated using eq. (5) and wind tunnel test data. In order to consider first two modes, Butterworth band-pass filter (2 ~ 27 Hz) was used. The evaluated flutter boundary and analytic result are shown in Table 2. It can be inferred that the stability boundary is about 15.0 m/s. The predicted flutter boundary is slightly less than analytical result like modal frequencies. The flutter prediction parameters for FBG sensor signal are shown in Fig. 9. The sampled data acquired in low speed region are small and include large amount of noise. Hence, they are not suitable for flutter prediction parameter estimation. Fig. 10 shows root-mean-square (RMS) values of displacement and FBG sensor signals. The RMS values tend to increase around $q = 130$ Pa ($U_\infty = 14.6$ m/s). Although RMS value can be another indicator of flutter boundary, it needs more data above critical speed.

Table 2. Flutter boundary evaluation results.

	Laser sensor A	PVDF	FBG	V-g analysis
q_F [Pa]	134.7	138.8	137.5	.
V_F [m/s]	14.8	15.1	15.0	15.4

Figure 9. Estimation results using experimental data.

Figure 10. RMS values of displacement and FBG sensor signals.

The flutter suppression experiment has been performed at $U_\infty = 15.0$ m/s and $U_\infty = 17.0$ m/s. The designed neural network controller is implemented using a DSP board (DS1102, dSPACE) and the weights are updated at every 0.01 sec. Before wind tunnel testing, control performance was validated through impulsive loading without airflow. The FBG sensor signal is used as feedback signal and the control result is shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11. Control result for impulsive loading.

Figure 12. Flutter suppression result in frequency domain ($U_\infty = 15.0$ m/s).

Fig. 12 shows the power spectra at $U_\infty = 15.0$ m/s. The peak value at 16.1 Hz is reduced by using a neural-network controller. As the airflow velocity is increased to $U_\infty = 17.0$ m/s, the amplitude of vibration increases and the resonant frequency is slightly changed to 16.8 Hz. Control results at $U_\infty = 17.0$ m/s are shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14. The amplitudes of flutter mode and its harmonics are significantly reduced and the stability boundary is increased.

Figure 13. Flutter suppression result in time domain ($U_\infty = 17.0$ m/s).

Figure 14. Flutter suppression result in frequency domain ($U_\infty = 17.0$ m/s).

CONCLUSIONS

The present study investigates dynamic application of an FBG sensor system and the adaptive flutter control of a swept-back composite plate with a surface-bonded FBG sensor and piezoelectric actuators. An FBG sensor system with optically passive Fabry-Perot read-out interferometers is used to detect Bragg wavelength changes. The FBG sensor signal is used for the evaluation of aeroelastic

stability boundary and the suppression of flutter. A flutter prediction parameter calculated using sampled FBG sensor data shows reliable stability boundary of an aeroelastic system. The real-time neuro-adaptive control algorithm effectively reduces the amplitude of flutter mode and the stability boundary could be increased.

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